

Advantages of Teaching General Academic Vocabulary through Prose to Higher Secondary Students

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Abstract

Prose is a form of written or spoken language that uses a natural flow of speech and a grammatical structure. Academic Vocabulary is defined as words that are traditionally used in academic texts and dialogues. Particularly, those words are used to explain the academic concept only and do not appear in informal conversation. In common, every second language learner struggles to learn Academic Vocabulary. Prose works are one of the most important aspects of English literature. Prose works help secondary students learn academic words very quickly because prose works are in their best exploratory order. In addition, prose develops the language skills of listening, speaking, reading, and writing. Prose makes cognitive and affective aspects of the students. Prose is used to enable students to read texts with correct pronunciation, intonation, stress, pause, and articulation of voice. With the help of reading, students easily understand the meaning of the word. Prose is one of the most important teaching materials to be used for teaching Academic Vocabulary to secondary students.

Keywords: Academic Vocabulary, prose works, reading practice, secondary students, and advantages.

Introduction

Vocabulary is the fuel of the English language; without vocabulary, there is nothing meaningful; one cannot understand texts or communicate with others. Without vocabulary, second language learners cannot improve their language skills of listening, speaking, reading, and writing. Vocabulary is the major tool one is able to acquire the second language. When students are going to learn a vocabulary, they should distinguish between direct and indirect vocabulary. Direct vocabulary is based on the learner's activities, and they do exercises based on their vocabulary learning. Such exercises include vocabulary games, class work, and guessing words from the text book. But indirect vocabulary is based on learner and speaker communications.

Academic Vocabulary is the kind of vocabulary that frequently appears in academic disciplines, and is rarely available in day-to-day conversation. Academic Vocabulary is critical to understanding the concept of content taught in schools. Academic Vocabulary reveals to students the word, reference, abstract concept, and meaning of the words. Academic Vocabulary helps students overcome many major problems in the academic field. When the student lacks adequate vocabulary, they have difficulties in understanding the meaning of words in texts. Here, the study uses prose works to teach Academic Vocabulary to secondary students because prose works create interest and give new knowledge. Here, prose is used to develop students' cognitive and affective aspects. Cognitive aspects are based on the process of understanding or related to the process of cognition. Another affective aspect is based on the student's emotions, moods, and feelings. Prose's best meaning is to preserve human experience, imagination, ideas, and knowledge. A simple prose work, which means one or two-page prose works, makes reading interesting to students. When students read a prose continuously in ESL classrooms after its change, like a habit, their vocabulary is automatically developed.

Teaching General Academic Vocabulary

Academic vocabulary is commonly used to refer to words in academic contexts. Academic vocabulary is used to develop the knowledge of the students in a particular subject or an area of knowledge or activity. Academic vocabulary is generally divided into two types: general academic vocabulary and technical academic vocabulary. Technical academic vocabulary is needed in academic contexts. Technical academic vocabulary covers all the areas of study, for example, inertia (used in physics), photosynthesis (used in biology), and externalities (used in economics).

The research is focuses on general academic vocabulary. General academic vocabulary is a kind of vocabulary that has a list of words, and those words are commonly used in academic contexts. For example, in the sentence “the aims of the study are,” “aim” and “study” are general academic vocabulary. In a common statement, general academic vocabulary words have the meaning of two sides in academic as well as general.

The example of the word “discipline” having a general meaning is to train people to obey, but in academic use, it means a subject of study. Vocabulary is the key component of academic language, so the teacher must be familiar with general academic words. General academic vocabulary makes use of all the areas of academic context and materials and is not necessarily relevant to one specific content area. Those words must be seemingly common in academic contexts and may also change the meaning of the words, such as table or process. For example, general academic words are analysis, objectives, critique, evidence, except, precise, and trace.

Advantages of Prose Works

Prose is written in the form of improving words, forms, grammar, and vocabulary. The main aim of using prose in the English language classroom is to develop the language abilities of the students. Prose is the complete study of the language. The language ability helps the learners use the English language without any problems.

In education a variety of text books are used to teach a second language. Through the text books, various language skills are developed, such as listening, speaking, reading, and writing. There is no doubt that teaching vocabulary without text books is unnecessary and a waste of time and energy. If the textbook is used to teach vocabulary in the classroom, it is beneficial for the teacher and the learners.

Prose works such as fiction, non-fiction, essays, and narratives offer several advantages for improving general academic vocabulary in the ESL (English as a Second Language) classroom. These texts provide a natural, engaging, and varied context for learning and using vocabulary, helping students develop the academic language skills needed for success in higher education. Below are the key benefits of using prose works to enhance general academic vocabulary.

1. Contextualized Vocabulary Learning

Prose exposes students to academic vocabulary in context, helping them understand not just the definition of words but also their appropriate usage. Seeing how words function in real academic contexts, such as in essays, articles, or narratives, enables learners to comprehend the nuances of the language, which can be difficult to grasp from isolated vocabulary lists.

2. Wide Exposure to Academic Vocabulary across Disciplines

Prose works often span a wide range of topics, from the humanities and social sciences to scientific and historical contexts. This diversity helps ESL students encounter academic vocabulary across multiple disciplines, expanding their ability to understand and use language in various academic fields.

3. Repetition and Reinforcement of Key Academic Terms

Prose works often repeat important academic vocabulary, which reinforces learning. Repeated exposure to key terms helps students internalize the vocabulary and increases their ability to recall and use it when needed.

4. Understanding of Word Collocations and Phrasal Structures

Academic vocabulary is often used in **collocations that means**, words that commonly appear together and prose works give students exposure to these natural combinations. Understanding these collocations is key to using academic vocabulary effectively, as students learn to pair words correctly and understand how phrases are structured in academic contexts.

5. Development of Reading Fluency and Academic Literacy

Regular reading of prose not only helps students acquire vocabulary but also improves their reading fluency. Fluent readers can quickly identify and comprehend academic vocabulary, making it easier to understand complex academic texts. As students engage with different types of prose, their overall reading comprehension and academic literacy increase.

6. Improvement in Writing Skills through Exposure to Academic Language

By reading academic prose, ESL students gain insights into the style and structure of academic writing, which helps them incorporate new vocabulary into their own writing. They learn how to use academic terms appropriately and in context, which enhances their writing skills for essays, reports, and research papers.

7. Cultural and Conceptual Knowledge for Academic Discussions

Many academic terms are closely tied to specific cultural or conceptual frameworks. Prose works often explore ideas that are central to academic discourse—such as identity, society, ethics, and history—and provide students with the vocabulary needed to discuss these concepts thoughtfully in academic settings.

And also prose is used to improve the language skills of listening, reading, writing, speaking, there are given below;

Reading

One of the best ways to increase vocabulary is for students to read a text carefully, reading each sentence until they understand it. As a teacher, focus on the rereading section of the students because it can help them fulfil their vocabulary needs. Apart from reading, students must learn keywords; it will add more knowledge to their vocabulary. The teacher must encourage students to read the prose several times if needed. Repeated reading of the text book reveals what they have missing vocabulary meaning about the first time. Prose works encourage them to write unknown and long words. As a result, they must know five or six words in a single text.

Listening and Speaking

Listening is the first and best skill for students to improve their vocabulary. Once the students have the chance to read a texts on their own, they learn more words, and class discussion is one of the best ways to understand further vocabulary. When the students listen to new words uttered by the teacher in the ESL classroom, it must be fixed in their minds. Students communicate with classmates, which may improve their vocabulary. When all the students read a prose in the class room and tell about their opinion and understanding, a variety of opinions can help the meaning of vocabulary. Teacher lectures help students understand the materials, but creating a discussion involves students more effectively in learning vocabulary. During the class, asking questions with the teacher and friends is also one way to gain vocabulary.

Writing

One of the best ways for students to increase their vocabulary is to write down what they read and understand. Students must keep their class work books with themes and free-write paragraphs immediately after completing the reading. Another

one is writing the meaning of the words, which also enhance creative and critical thinking in English. After completing class work, teachers should ask them to find another meaning of the word, which is the best way to improve their vocabulary.

Prose Helping in Verity of Activities

Using prose to enhance general academic vocabulary in an ESL classroom can be very effective because prose naturally incorporates a range of academic words that students need for their studies. Prose includes various forms, such as novels, short stories, essays, and even non-fiction excerpts, making it a flexible tool for vocabulary teaching. Here are some strategies for leveraging prose to improve general academic vocabulary:

1. Contextualized Vocabulary Instruction through Reading Comprehension Activities

Academic vocabulary is best learned in context. When students read a prose text, select specific academic vocabulary words within the reading and design activities around them. For instance, if a short story uses the word "analyse," have students examine how it's used in context, discuss its meaning, and create sentences using the word in similar contexts. This not only enhances understanding but helps students see the word's usage in a real-life setting.

Example Activity: Choose a paragraph with words like "contrast," "interpret," and "conclude." Create comprehension questions that require students to use these words to answer, thus reinforcing vocabulary comprehension and application.

2. Vocabulary Mapping and Word Analysis

Use prose as a springboard for vocabulary mapping, where students break down new academic words they encounter. Have them identify root words, prefixes, and suffixes, which can help them guess meanings and recognize similar academic vocabulary. For example, words like "construct," "reconstruct," and "construction" from a text allow students to analyse the word family and deepen their understanding.

Example Activity: After reading a text with the word “predict,” students can complete a word map that includes its part of speech, synonyms (e.g., "forecast"), related forms ("prediction," "predictable"), and a sentence using the word.

3. Close Reading

Close reading is a technique where students examine a short passage from prose in great detail. In this approach, students focus on how the language conveys meaning, including academic words and phrases. Discussing why specific words were chosen or how they support the text’s tone and purpose can make students more comfortable with academic vocabulary and enhance their critical reading skills.

Example Activity: Give students a paragraph and ask them to identify all the academic words. Discuss how each word contributes to the overall meaning of the passage, encouraging them to use similar words in their own sentences.

4. Interactive Vocabulary Exercises like Role-Play or Re-enactment

Role-play based on prose texts can encourage students to use academic vocabulary in context. After reading a short story or an excerpt, have students perform or narrate a scene using academic vocabulary. Assigning roles like “analyst,” “summarizer,” or “critic” encourages students to actively use words they encounter, such as “interpret,” “compare,” or “summarize.”

Example Activity: After reading a prose excerpt with rich descriptive language, students can role-play characters discussing the themes. Encourage them to use words like "evaluate," "justify," or "evidence" in their dialogues, reinforcing vocabulary in an interactive way.

5. Summarization and Paraphrasing Activities

Summarizing or paraphrasing prose texts helps students practice academic vocabulary. When summarizing, students must distil main ideas and express them concisely, which often requires using general academic terms like “main idea,”

“sequence,” and “evidence.” Paraphrasing, similarly, encourages students to restate the author’s ideas using academic synonyms.

Example Activity: Assign a passage and ask students to summarize it using target vocabulary words like "identify," "explain," and "summarize." Discuss their summaries, encouraging them to rephrase using alternative academic terms when needed.

6. Using Graphic Organizers for Analysing Prose Vocabulary

Graphic organizers such as T-charts, Venn diagrams, or concept maps can help students visualize relationships between academic vocabulary and content in prose. For instance, when comparing characters or themes, a Venn diagram using words like “compare,” “contrast,” “feature,” and “characteristic” reinforces academic vocabulary in an analytical context.

Example Activity: After reading a story with two contrasting characters, use a Venn diagram to compare them. Students to use academic terms like "difference," "similarity," and "contrast" to describe their analysis.

7. Sentence Completion and Transformation Exercises

After identifying academic vocabulary in a prose text, create sentence-completion or transformation exercises that encourage students to practice using the vocabulary in new contexts. Sentence-completion activities help solidify understanding by requiring students to use the word meaningfully, while transformations help them recognize how academic words can adapt to different sentence structures.

Example Activity: Provide sentences with academic words from the prose text, with one or more words missing, and have students complete them. For transformation, provide a sentence like "The character interprets the event as surprising," and ask students to rewrite it using "interpretation" or "interpreted."

8. Frequent Vocabulary Recycling and Review

To reinforce retention, revisit academic vocabulary from prose regularly. Use words from previous lessons in new prose texts or through vocabulary quizzes, games, and discussions. Frequent recycling helps make academic words part of students' active vocabulary.

Example Activity: Start each class with a “word review” of key academic terms from previous readings. Engage students in a quick activity, like a matching game, that pairs words with definitions or sample sentences. These strategies allow teachers to use prose as a rich resource for academic vocabulary instruction, making vocabulary acquisition engaging, contextualized, and practical for students.

General Objectives of Prose Works

- To enable the students to understand the passage and meaning of the sentence.
- To enable the students to read the text book without errors in correct pronunciation, stress, intonation, pause, and articulation of voice.
- To enable the learners to understand the text with the help of silent reading.
- To improve their active and passive vocabulary.
- To enable the learners to deliver their ideas in speaking as well as in writing.
- To enable the learners to enjoy reading and writing.
- To develop learners imagination.
- To prepare the students for communicating with others.

Specific Objectives of Prose Works

- To develop general academic vocabulary for higher secondary students.
- To promote their intensive reading.
- To develop a clear idea about the new words.
- To familiarise students with new academic terms.
- To develop their confidence to communicate with others with the help of learning academic vocabulary.

- Short prose works develop their interest in reading.
- To gain knowledge about a new academic word list.
- To clarify the meaning of difficult words, phrases, and idioms.
- To promote their interest in knowing about new academic vocabulary.

Conclusion

Vocabulary plays a major role when students improve their skills of listening, reading, speaking, and writing. Given the high importance of vocabulary in instruction, teachers should use every available opportunity to emphasise key words in the classroom. General academic vocabulary is a list of words that make use of various academic contexts. As teachers begin to improve the general academic vocabulary of the students in their speech and writing, the students definitely follow it. In general, prose means to create human knowledge, imagination, experience, and ideas. Prose is one of the easiest ways to increase a vocabulary because it gives clear ideas about new words. Prose works commonly develop the skills of listening, reading, writing, and speaking, encourages critical thinking, and creates an interest in learning new vocabularies.

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